

AUSTRALIA'S ROLE IN DEVELOPING INDONESIA'S CAPACITY BUILDING IN COMBATTING NARCOTIC CRIMES

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Abstract

This research seeks to explain Australia's role, through the Australian Federal Police (AFP) and the Australian Border Force (ABF) in developing Indonesian National Narcotics Board's (BNN) capacity building in dealing with narcotics crimes. Special skills are needed in dealing with narcotics crimes, both in the process of prosecution of criminals and crime prevention. The Indonesian National Narcotics Board faced several obstacles in handling narcotic crimes, including the lack of capacity in using technology to identify new kinds of drugs and capability to track down narcotic criminals. Hence, Australia observes that enforcement skills could be developed within Indonesia's capacity to deal with narcotics crimes. This study uses a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach to describe Australia's role in developing Indonesia's internal and external capacity building. The result of this research shows that Australia's role in developing Indonesia's capacity building through conducting activities in the form of training which consists of skills, knowledge and attitude training. Australia's training has improved BNN staff's internal capacity in problem solving, integrity and knowledge. Australia has also improved BNN's external capacity by developing K-9 facilities and granting dog runs.

Keywords: Indonesian National Narcotics Board, Australian Federal Police, Australian Border Force, Capacity Building, Countering Narcotic Crimes

INTRODUCTION

This study seeks to explain Australia's role, through the Australian Federal Police (AFP) and the Australian Border Force (ABF) in developing Indonesian National Narcotics Board's (BNN) capacity building in combatting narcotic crimes. Indonesia and Australia are both located between two oceans, making them geographically prone to drugs trafficking and smuggling¹. Thus, the neighboring countries need to cooperate in dealing with transnational narcotic crimes².

Indonesia and Australia had diplomatic relations since 1949. Previously, both governments have signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on Combating Transnational Crime and Developing Police Cooperation. This MoU was signed on 13 June and ratified in September 2002, which became the formal framework for cooperation in law enforcement between the two countries³. Cooperation in combatting narcotic crimes between the two countries continued, through the signing of MoU between the Australian Federal Police (AFP) and Indonesia's National Narcotics Agency (BNN) in 2011, followed by another MoU signed by the Australian Border Force (ABF) and Indonesia's National Narcotics Agency in 2018⁴.

Despite the strong bilateral relations between Indonesia and Australia, both countries have faced several problems related to narcotic crimes. For instance, in 2005 there was the Bali Nine case, when nine Australians smuggled drugs to Bali, Indonesia. Despite Australia's protest, Indonesia executed two criminals who became the mastermind of the Bali Nine case in 2015 after ten years of judicial process⁵.

Indonesia's death sentence towards Australian drug smugglers affected cooperation between Indonesia and Australia. Before the Bali Nine case, BNN's cooperation with AFP

¹ Mangai Natarajan, *Kejahatan Dan Pengadilan Internasional* (Bandung : Nusa Media, 2015) 345

² Putriani Sholihatun Nisa, "Interview by a Customs officer in the sub-section of Indonesia-Australia International Cooperation." 3 November 2022,

https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfIpe

³ Australian Federal Police, *Submission No 62: Inquiry Into Australia's Relations with Indonesia*. (Canberra: Australian Federal Police, 2003). 6

⁴ The hon Brendan O'connor MP, *nota kesepahaman untuk memerangi perdagangan obat-obatan terlarang*, (2011) https://indonesia.embassy.gov.au/jaktindonesian/SMHAJM11_002.html

⁵ CNN Indonesia, *Memori atas kasus Bali Nine Sindikat penyelundup narkoba*, (2018)

<https://www.cnnindonesia.com/nasional/20181121135528-12-348095/memori-atas-kasus-bali-nine-sindikat-penyelundup-narkoba>

and ABF have significantly contributed towards countering narcotic crimes through joint operation and information sharing. But after the Bali Nine case, Australia limited information sharing with Indonesia. Since then, Australia focused on developing Indonesia's capacity building in countering narcotic crimes⁶. BNN admitted that Indonesia needs to improve capacity building in combatting narcotic crimes, such as technology to identify drugs, laboratory facilities, and increased funding⁷. Australia agreed that by improving Indonesia's capacity building in combatting transnational organized crimes, there will be less drugs trafficking to Australia⁸. The Bali Nine case happened since 2005 until 2015, and this research examined Australia's role in developing Indonesia's capacity building in combatting narcotic crimes from 2016 until 2021.

METHOD

This research used a descriptive qualitative method to examine Australia's role in developing Indonesia's capacity building in countering narcotic crimes. Descriptive qualitative method's purpose is to describe, find out and understand social or humanities phenomenon⁹. This research's time frame focuses after the Bali Nine case, which altered Indonesia and Australia's relations from joint cooperation in combatting narcotic crimes into Australia giving assistance to develop Indonesia's capacity building in law enforcement. Data collecting process took place from September until December 2022, from official documents and online interviews with BNN. The subject of research includes the Australian Federal Police (AFP) and Australian Border Force (ABF).

This research utilizes the role concept to discuss Australia's role in assisting Indonesia, as well as capacity building concept to describe Indonesia's capacity in law enforcement, and cooperation in countering narcotic crimes. Soekanto explained that role

⁶ Tri Wahono, "Peranan Polri Dalam Pencegahan Dan Pemberantasan Penyalahgunaan Peredaran Gelap Narkoba Di Wilayah Hukum Polres Boyolali (Studi Kasus Di Polres Boyolali)", *Jurnal Bedah Hukum*, Vol.3, No.2 (2019) 3

⁷ Ira Helviza, "Kendala-Kendala Badan Narkotika Nasional (Bnn) Dalam Penanggulangan Penyalahgunaan Narkotika Di Kota Banda Aceh", *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Pendidikan Kewarganegaraan Unsyiah*, Vol. 1, No. 1, (2016) 125

⁸ H. Iskandar Hasan and Nina Naramurti, *Kerjasama Kepolisian dan Penegakan Hukum Internasional*, (Jakarta: PT Firris Bahtera Perkasa, 2013) 148

⁹ Creswell W. John, *Research Design Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif, dan Mixed*. (Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar, 2013) 12

means somebody's capability to do his or her rights and responsibilities in life¹⁰. Meanwhile Biddle and Thomas explained that role is divided into four categories, specifically: somebody or a group contributing towards social interaction; an action as a result of interaction; position of somebody in an interaction; and between individual and his or her action¹¹. Whereas Andarmoyo argued that role means action conducted by an actor according to his or her responsibility¹².

On the other hand, Brown explained that capacity building is a process to increase somebody's capacity, group, organization or system to complete a task better than before¹³. According to the United Nations, capacity building means an effort to improve capacity from an individual, group, or organization to achieve better¹⁴. Improving capacity building requires problem identification and finding solution, by providing professional skills training, technical assistance, and strengthening network¹⁵.

Capacity building according to Enemark has three dimensions: Individual level which includes human resource development through training; Entity level which include the government, private sector and informal organization; as well as System level which involve all countries and society, subcomponents, law and order, managerial perspective, accountability and available human resources. Capacity building could be developed in some aspects¹⁶: Internal aspects such as improving capability in problem solving, skills in making use of technology and leadership, as well as behavior such as communication, discipline, professional, and responsibility; External aspects include facilities and tools to support work, facilities construction and repairs.

¹⁰ Soekanto, Soerjono. *Sosiologi Suatu Pengantar*, (Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada, 2006) 213

¹¹ Biddle, B.J dan Thomas, E.J, *Role Theory : Concept and Research* (New York : Wiley, 1966)

¹² Andarmoyo, Sulisty. *Keperawatan Keluarga Konsep Teori, Proses dan Praktik Keperawatan* (Yogyakarta : Graha Ilmu, 2012) Hal. 4

¹³ Brown, Lisanne, et. Al, *Measuring Capacity Building, Carolina population Center, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill* (2001) 8

¹⁴ United Nations, *Capacity Building*, (2011) <https://www.un.org/en/academic-impact/capacity-building>

¹⁵ 43M Digital, *pengertian capacity building dan contoh penerapannya*, (2020)

<https://www.materidigital.com/pengertian-capacity-building-dan-contoh-penerapannya/>

¹⁶ Douglas Norton, Anastasia Alexaxi. et all, *Evaluating Capacity Development, ISNAR (international service for National Agricultural research*, (Netherland: 2003) <http://www.isnar.cgiar.org>

Table 1. Indonesia's Capacity Building in Countering Narcotic Crimes

Capacity	Indonesia's Capacity Building before cooperating with Australia	Indonesia's Capacity Building after cooperating with Australia
Internal Capacity	Capability: problem solving (preventive & arresting criminals); knowledge (domestic narcotic crimes)	Capability: problem solving (K-9, ship searching, tracking gangs); knowledge (training on transnational & narcotic crimes, dark web, enforcement, tracking gangs & criminal motives)
	Skills: technology (laboratory, detection, dark web); leadership (discipline & consistency)	Skills: technology (dark web, social media); leadership (leadership training)
	Behavior: responsibility	Behavior: professionalism
External Capacity	Facilities: laboratory, K-9 tactical building	Facilities: dog runs & K-9

Source: adopted by authors from Enemark, S. 2003. Understanding the Concept of Capacity Building and the Nature of Land Administration Systems. FIG Working Week, 5.

Based on the indicators above, there are two aspects to capacity building, which are internal and external capacity. From both aspects, Indonesia, specifically BNN has internal capacity in problem solving and knowledge to combat narcotic crimes. In terms of skills, BNN has technological and leadership capacity. In terms of behavior, BNN conducts its work responsibly. Additionally, BNN possesses external capacity to support its mission by utilizing facilities such as laboratory and K-9 tactical building. In both aspects, BNN's capacity needs to be improved.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Indonesia's Capacity in Countering Narcotic Crimes before Cooperating with Australia

The Indonesian National Narcotics Board (BNN) is authorized in dealing with narcotic crimes, and capable of cooperating with other countries¹⁷. BNN needs to develop its capacity building, especially in terms of human resources. Specifically, BNN staff still

¹⁷ BNN, nd, Profil BNN, (2020) 24-27 https://perpustakaan.bnn.go.id/sites/default/files/Buku_Digital_2020-08/Profil_Badan_Narkotika_Nasional.pdf

require additional knowledge in understanding recent transnational organized crime motives, as well as improved foreign language proficiency.

BNN's Internal Capacity include: Capability in problem solving through preventive action and prosecution of narcotic criminals. Preventive action is done by raising society's awareness, especially in schools and universities about the dangers of narcotic drugs to prevent drug abuse. BNN also provided counselling, rehabilitation and training sessions for victims of drug abuse¹⁸. One of BNN's required skills is on how to train tracking dogs (K-9) in detecting drugs carried by smugglers¹⁹. Previously only Indonesian customs has K-9 capability. Next in terms of knowledge, BNN staff's foreign language ability needs to be improved, especially English to understand the development of transnational crimes and to counter drugs trafficking and smuggling²⁰. Mrs. Rika Motota, BNN's staff on Indonesia-Australia cooperation, explained that not all of BNN staffs have proficient foreign language capability²¹. During the Bali Nine case, there were some document mistranslations during trial, which caused delayed law enforcement of the case until 2010²². Therefore, BNN needs to strengthen tracing ability and English proficiency²³.

In terms of skills, BNN needs to improve their technological and leadership capacity. Narcotic criminals utilize technology to hide drugs and ease narcotic transactions. To anticipate it, BNN has established a laboratory to identify different kinds of drugs²⁴. BNN has also used technology to map and track down narcotic syndicates²⁵. Before cooperating with Australia, the United States (US) assisted BNN to develop its capacity in analyzing dark web, or market places which provide illegal services including drugs trade.

¹⁸ BNN, *Upaya Sindikat Narkoba dan Upaya menghindari Narkoba*, (2021) <https://sumsel.bnn.go.id/upaya-sindikat-narkoba-upaya-menghindari-narkoba/>

¹⁹ Handoyo, P., & Irawati, I. "40 Tahun "Perang Melawan Narkotika": Pengelolaan Narkotika oleh Negara, Perang Bukan Solusi". *Jurnal Peradilan Indonesia*, 5(1), (2014) 34.

²⁰ Peraturan Presiden Republik Indonesia Nomor 23 Tahun 2010 Tentang Badan Narkotika Nasional, <http://www.bphn.go.id/data/documents/10pr023.pdf>

²¹ Rika Motota, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022, https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfIpe

²² Detiknews, *Salah Terjemahan Sidang Kasus Bali nine ditunda*, (2010) <https://news.detik.com/berita/d-1352967/salah-terjemahan-sidang-kasus-narkoba-anggota-bali-nine-ditunda>

²³ Amaritasari, I. P. "Keamanan Nasional dalam Konteks Isu-isu Global Kontemporer: Sebuah Tinjauan Hubungan Internasional". *Jurnal Keamanan Nasional*, 3(1), (2017). 109–132. <https://doi.org/10.31599/jkn.v3i1.19> hal. 6

²⁴ BNN, nd, *Laporan Laboratorium BNN*, https://laboratorium.bnn.go.id/asset/ppid/LKIP_.pdf

²⁵ Fathiyah Wardah, *Indonesia di duga jadi sasaran transaksi narkotika online*, (2012) <https://www.voaindonesia.com/a/indonesia-diduga-jadi-sasaran-transaksi-narkotika-online--I143476876/106349.html>

However, there are still insufficient number of BNN staffs capable of analyzing dark web, with lack of technological facilities²⁶. Mrs. Farranthi Shavitri and Mrs. Rika Motota, BNN staffs on Indonesia-Australia cooperation, stated that from 2005 until 2015, not all BNN staffs were capable of using technology to track down dark web or identify intelligence²⁷.

Since its establishment in 2002, BNN's leadership skills could be seen from its consistency in decision-making. For instance, BNN supported death penalty for drug traffickers during the Bali Nine case in 2005²⁸. This decision was taken to prevent similar cases from happening in the future. As a response, Australia protested Indonesia's death penalty decision and withdrew its ambassador to Indonesia. On the behavioral aspect, BNN faced some problems when there were some staffs which sold and misused drugs taken from arrested criminals, which decreased BNN's reputation²⁹.

On the other hand, BNN's External Capacity include facilities to support its mission. BNN has a laboratory used to identify different kinds of drugs in Indonesia³⁰. BNN also had a tactical building for tracker dogs (K-9), but with limited funding to build a dog runs facility for K-9. There are also still limited number of police dogs owned by BNN, without having the capability to breed them³¹.

Australia's Role in Developing Indonesia's Capacity in Countering Narcotic Crimes

Australia has better capacity building than Indonesia in terms of technology, tracking method and problem-solving skills in countering narcotic crimes³². Therefore, AFP and ABF's assistance has improved BNN's capacity in countering narcotic crimes.

²⁶ BNN, *Darknet ruang kejahatan upaya memerangi narkoba bijak*, (2021) <https://ntb.bnn.go.id/darknet-ruang-kejahatan-upaya-memerangi-narkoba-bijak/>

²⁷ Rika Motota and Farranthi Shavitri, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022,

https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfIpe

²⁸ Kompas, *BNN dukung dua terpidana kasus bali nine segera dihukum mati*, (2025)

<https://regional.kompas.com/read/2015/01/21/12584611/BNN.Dukung.Dua.Terpidana.Bali.Nine.Segera.Dihukum.Mati>

²⁹ CNN, *Dua Pegawai BNN Diduga Jual Barang Bukti Narkoba* (2014)

<https://www.cnnindonesia.com/nasional/20141018183244-32-440794/dua-pegawai-bnn-diduga-jual-barang-bukti-narkoba>

³⁰ BNN, nd, *pusat laboratorium BNN*, <https://laboratorium.bnn.go.id/>

³¹ Iqbal Muhtarom, *pasukan k-9 punya gedung baru*, (2021) <https://metro.tempo.co/read/1651627/pasukan-k-9-punya-gedung-baru-fadil-imran-apresiasi-kinerja-anjing-pelacak>

³² Australian Strategic Policy Institute. *Australia's Illicit Drug Problem is Getting Worse*.

<https://www.aspistrategist.org.au/australias-illicit-drugproblem-is-getting-worse/>

AFP's role in Developing BNN's Capacity Building in Countering Narcotic Crimes

Initially, the Australian Federal Police (AFP) improved BNN's internal capacity, including BNN staff's human resource capability. AFP have trained BNN in problem solving, by tracking down motorcycle gangs through intelligence sharing. For instance, AFP and BNN have tracked down the Outlaw Motorcycle Gangs (OMCGs), which distribute illegal drugs in Australia, with some members residing in Bali³³.

In terms of knowledge, AFP have shared information on narcotic crimes' transnational development, to anticipate similar problems in other countries from happening domestically in Indonesia. AFP held online meetings to train BNN's staff on how to track down dark web, identifying and dealing with illegal sites³⁴. In 2020, AFP held an enforcement training on the dangers of transnational crime, especially drugs trafficking to strengthen the integrity of law enforcement bodies³⁵.

Despite tensions between Indonesia and Australia during the Bali Nine case, AFP still provided intelligence sharing to BNN annually, especially limited to narcotic criminals' motives based on cases of drugs trafficking to Australia from other countries. For instance, drugs from China were trafficked through the sea hidden in tea bags. Such information would increase BNN's law enforcement capacity to anticipate similar drugs smuggling motives from entering Indonesia³⁶.

English language proficiency is extremely important in tracing narcotic criminals. Australia stated that Indonesia faced language barriers in dealing with the Bali Nine case by mistranslating certain documents³⁷. Thus, AFP decided to organize English training for BNN and Indonesia's Customs³⁸. This training was held annually since 2019, by inviting Indonesian staffs to Australia. However, since the pandemic in 2020, this training continued

³³ Fathurrohman. (n.d.). *Konektivitas Jaringan Narkoba Indonesia – Australia*. (2022)

<https://kumparan.com/fathurrohman0920/konektivitas-jaringan-narkobaindonesia-australia-1ufvgtxC4EB/3>

³⁴ BNN, *pelatihan Dark web dan cryptocurrency dari Australia federal police*, (2019)

<https://jakselkota.bnn.go.id/pelatihan-dark-web-dan-cryptocurrency-dari-australian-federal-police-afp>

³⁵ Draft Tindak lanjut kerjasama yang tidak terpublish Indonesia dengan Australia, Tindak Lanjut Kerjasama (2021).pdf

³⁶ Rika Motota and Farranthi Shavitri, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022,

https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfIpe

³⁷ Detiknews, *Salah Terjemahan Sidang Kaus Bali nine ditunda* (2010) <https://news.detik.com/berita/d-1352967/salah-terjemahan-sidang-kasus-narkoba-anggota-bali-nine-ditunda>

³⁸ Farranthi Shavitri, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 20 November 2022, https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfIpe

to be held online³⁹.

AFP also trained BNN to improve their skills. Previously, Indonesia was assisted by the United States (US) in tracking down dark web. Dark web are hidden sites which provide illegal services anonymously to hide users' identity and to escape tracking from the government⁴⁰. To prevent dependency towards the US, BNN asked AFP to assist them in dark web tracing⁴¹. This training also talked about online drugs trade using crypto currency. Ms. Rika Motota explained that there is an increasing number of BNN staffs capable of tracing dark web, from 5 to 10 people⁴². Another annual training on social media and Open-Source Intelligence Training (OSINT) was also held by AFP to improve BNN staffs' skills in investigating digital data from social media⁴³.

In terms of leadership and behavioral aspects, Australia believes that Indonesia is consistent in law enforcement towards narcotic criminals. Nevertheless, AFP provided annual training since 2019 to prepare staffs to become the next BNN leaders. This training consists of leadership, managerial skills, professionalism and law enforcement in countering narcotic crimes strategically⁴⁴. Ms. Farranthi Shavitri and Ms. Rika Motota explained that BNN's newly recruited staffs need to act professionally in distinguishing professional and personal responsibilities. Even so, AFP has not contributed in updating BNN's external capacity, such as office facilities, since AFP's programs are mostly focused on human resource development of BNN's staff through annual programs.

ABF's role in Developing BNN's Capacity Building in Countering Narcotic Crimes

Australian Border Force (ABF) is Australia's customs institution, capable of enforcing law by tracking down drugs using technology and detector dogs. ABF has assisted Indonesia by improving BNN's internal capacity. In terms of capability, ABF has

³⁹ BNN, *International training of narcotics enforcement*, (2019) <https://ppsdm.bnn.go.id/international-training-of-narcotics-enforcement/>

⁴⁰ Kaspersky, *Is the Dark Web Dangerous? What you need to know* | Kaspersky. Kaspersky. (2021) <https://www.kaspersky.com/resourcecenter/threats/deep-web>

⁴¹ History of the AFP | Australian Federal Police, (2021) from <https://www.afp.gov.au/about-us/our-organisation/history-afp>

⁴² Interview BNN, (2022) https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfI

⁴³ Humas BNN, BNN RI – AFP Gelar Social Media and Open-Source Intelligence Training (OSINT) Tingkat Lanjutan, <https://bnn.go.id/50174-2/>

⁴⁴ Rika Motota, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022, https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfIpe

assisted BNN in problem solving, by signing an MoU in 2018 on developing canine training skills, management and breeding K-9 dogs⁴⁵. Countering narcotic crimes require detector dogs, also called canine (K-9) capable of detecting and tracking down drug possessions⁴⁶.

ABF has also helped BNN in vessel search training. Indonesia's maritime geography makes the country prone to drugs smuggling using fishing and cargo vessels through harbors without being noticed by customs. ABF provides training to develop Indonesian staff in detecting drugs in ships. This training involved safety procedure, environmental observation, identifying and investigating suspicious vessels and cruise ships⁴⁷. By participating in this training, BNN is capable of investigating ships carrying illicit drugs through the ocean.

ABF improved BNN's knowledge, by organizing webinar series on transnational and serious organized crime (TSOC). ABF provides this training in 2021 for BNN, which discussed the coming of drugs trafficking, money laundering, countering terrorism, violent extremism, supply chain security & cyber security and how to counter those transnational problems. Weak law enforcement in terms of border protection became the main problem⁴⁸.

Additionally, ABF provided intelligence sharing on how drug traffickers hide drugs. Although intelligence sharing between Indonesia and Australia suspended due to the Bali Nine case, ABF provided information to BNN related to the different kinds of drugs, and the field of customs, based on the new strategies used by narcotic criminals in smuggling drugs to Australia⁴⁹. Besides that, ABF also provided English language proficiency training for BNN staff, to ease information sharing related to narcotic crimes. This training was conducted since 2018, by sending BNN staff to Australia, and also online.

In terms of skills, ABF is capable of using technology for border protection and customs, unlike BNN. ABF doesn't provide this training due to the difference of work aspects between the two institutions. Even so, ABF provided leadership training to BNN in

⁴⁵BNN, *Optimalisasi Breeding untuk cetak pasukan K-9 hebat*, (2020) <https://bnn.go.id/optimalisasi-breeding-untuk-cetak-pasukan-k9-hebat/>

⁴⁶ Handoyo, P., & Irawati, I. "40 Tahun "Perang Melawan Narkotika": Pengelolaan Narkotika oleh Negara, Perang Bukan Solusi. *Jurnal Peradilan Indonesia*", 5(1), (2016), 34.

⁴⁷ Putriani Sholihatun Nisa, "Interview by Indonesian Customs Officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia International Cooperation", https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfI

⁴⁸ Admin BNN, *Webinar Series Transnational Organised crime*, (2021) <https://kalbar.bnn.go.id/webinar-series-transnational-organised-crime/>

⁴⁹ Rika Motota, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022 https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfI

2019 to develop strategic leadership, knowledge in response towards narcotic crimes, educating future leaders in predicting potential incidents⁵⁰. On the behavioral aspect, ABF also provided professionalism training on ethical code on problem solving, law enforcement, to increase society's trust towards BNN⁵¹.

Finally, ABF improved BNN's External Capacity. ABF provided grant to BNN in the form of dog runs, fenced facilities being built in BNN's current K-9 training ground, including 20 dog runs unit with 3x9 meter dimension per unit⁵². Previously BNN had limited dog runs facility. Besides that, ABF also gave five tracker dogs to BNN⁵³. In short, Cooperation between Indonesia and Australia have positive result towards improving BNN's capacity building in improving skills, knowledge, behavior of law enforcements in countering narcotic crimes. Australia responded Indonesia's demand for organizing training despite diplomatic tension previously.

CONCLUSION

Indonesia cooperated with Australia to improve BNN's capacity building. Australia provided training, which include internal capacity such as skills training to improve BNN staffs' problem-solving skills, increased number of staff whom participated in the training from 5 to 10 members, less violation by law enforcers in misusing drugs, improved integrity and knowledge of BNN staff. Training future BNN leaders in countering narcotic crimes.

Australia has also improved BNN's external capacity, by providing facilities for K-9 by granting dog runs and tracker dogs to BNN. This research concludes that Australia has significant role in improving Indonesia's capacity building (BNN) in countering narcotic crimes. Increased number of BNN staffs which participated in training with improved skills, wider knowledge, increased integrity, and developed facilities.

⁵⁰ Farranthi Shavitri, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022 https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfI

⁵¹ Rika Motota and Farranthi Shavitri, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022 https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfI

⁵² Rika Motota, "Interview By BNN officer, sub-section of Indonesia-Australia international cooperation", 15 November 2022 https://drive.google.com/folderview?id=1siPPrSGjppq9rgpq9Y48c2O_TyU6MYfI

⁵³ BNN, *Tingkatkan Pertahanan dari Narkoba Australia Support K-9*, (2019) <https://bnn.go.id/tingkatkan-pertahanan-dari-narkoba-australia-support-k9/>

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- BNN. *pelatihan Dark web dan cryptocurrency dari Australia federal police*. 2019
<https://jakselkota.bnn.go.id/pelatihan-dark-web-dan-cryptocurrency-dari-australian-federal-police-afp>
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